

LASER-BASED 3D PRINTING: THE NEW FRONTIER OF PRECISION MANUFACTURING FOR FREE- FORM MICRO-OPTICS AND MINIATURIZED PHOTONIC SYSTEMS

Rolando Ferrini¹, Pietro Bernasconi,¹ Rosanna Toscano,¹ and Andrea Lovera¹

¹FEMTOprint SA, Via Industria 3, CH-6933 Muzzano, Switzerland

ABSTRACT

The FEMTOprint® technology is an innovative laser-based micro-machining technique for the production of glass micro-devices. This subtractive, direct-write fabrication process allows the creation of advanced 3D systems with micrometer precision and excellent repeatability. Here, we will show examples of fabricated (free-form) micro-optical components as well as of miniaturized photonic systems.

KEYWORDS: Micro-machining, 3D printing, Glass, Micro-optics, Photonics

INTRODUCTION

The fabrication of free-form micro-optical components faces important technological challenges that usually grow in the absence of symmetries, when the dimensions drop below the millimeter range and/or when the devices are arranged into densely packed arrays. In this context, the production of micro-devices with typical dimensions from a few microns to a few millimeters still poses rather significant technological issues. The FEMTOprint® micro-manufacturing platform solves some of the current manufacturing limitations, enabling the fabrication of arrays of free-form micro-lenses with good performance both in terms of shape accuracy and surface quality. This approach can produce truly 3D surfaces with both a few microns or less deviations from the nominal shape and surface qualities characterized by a roughness in the few nanometers range.

Moreover, the current miniaturization of photonic systems requires the access to advanced micro-fabrication technologies able both to guarantee high resolution and to enable a wide and cost-effective deployment, while maintaining and possibly increasing functionalities and performances. Here, the FEMTOprint® micro-fabrication technology enables 3D shape freedom in design, fast and cost-effective prototyping up to pilot and volume production, as well as the possibility of monolithically integrating several functionalities within a single photonic system, thus avoiding complex assembly steps, while allowing for a high level of complexity.

FREE-FORM MICRO-OPTICAL DEVICES

An array of spherical micro-lenses and a free-form micro-diffuser were fabricated, and their geometric characteristics were analyzed.

An array of about 100 spherical micro-lenses arranged in a closely packed hexagonal pattern was manufactured on a fused silica substrate. The lenses (Fig.1a) with a diameter of 500 μm and a radius of curvature RoC of 650 μm presented a SAG of 50 μm . The array was characterized via white-light interferometry by measuring a few lenses placed close to the center and to the top, bottom, left, and right portion of the array. The average RoC was measured to be in the order of 625 μm with a variation of $\pm 5 \mu\text{m}$, while the SAG matched the nominal value within $\pm 1.5 \mu\text{m}$. The achieved surface roughness Sa was measured to be smaller than 5 nm. Note that, while the obtained surface quality makes the array suitable for e.g. illumination applications, the shape accuracy in the order of a few hundreds of nanometers still requires optimization for these micro-lenses to be used for imaging applications.

An optical diffuser based on an array of free-form micro-lenses designed by CSEM was fabricated using our 3D manufacturing technique. The 2.5x2.5 mm² element (Fig.1b) consisted of free-form micro-lenses with variable diameters ranging between 50 and 70 μm and variable SAGs up to 70 μm .

The surface profile of the entire array was measured with a laser confocal scanning microscope and the deviation of the real device from the nominal shape was calculated using the Cloud-Compare software package. As shown in Figs.1c and 1d, the deviation is fairly uniform. In fact, the average deviation before the final surface processing is 0.08 μm with a standard deviation $\sigma = 1.27 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig.1d). These values increase after the surface treatment and grow to 0.15 μm and 1.71 μm , respectively. While the surface treatment in this case induces a deviation from the nominal shape, the surface roughness Sa drastically drops from approx. 250 nm to 20 nm or better. The device that has been obtained may thus be used as an optical diffuser with limited scattering.

Figure 1: (a) Detail of a fully processed micro-lens array. (b) Layout (left) and detail (right) of the free-form micro-diffuser. Top right is a sketch of the micro-lenses' profile. Surface deviation from nominal geometry (c) before and (d) after surface treatment (courtesy of CSEM).

MINIATURIZED PHOTONIC SYSTEMS

A miniaturized photonic system combining refractive and reflective optical elements (Figs.2a-d) was developed and fabricated for integration into a hybrid fluidic-optronic CMOS retina chip (Fig.2e) to improve its sensitivity in the optical detection of particle matter in air through the measurement of light scattering upon laser irradiation.

The optical system consists of front spherical elements, internal free-form reflectors, and flat back diopters (Fig.2d). These components are combined into a compact, monolithic element (Figs. 2b-c) that must provide both optical performance and stable mutual alignment. The monolithic optical device has a small footprint (Fig.2a), and the surfaces of all optical elements must have optical-grade quality. In particular, the miniaturized system includes out-of-plane micro-lenses, which are challenging to be produced using standard micro-fabrication methods. Moreover, free-form mirrors would require e.g. diamond turning, which is a very slow and expensive technique. The optical component was fabricated using the FEMTOprint® technology resulting into surfaces with a typical surface roughness S_a larger than 100 nm, not enough for optical components. The surface treatment was therefore applied to selectively reduce the S_a of the optical elements down to 5-15 nm, thus allowing for minimal surface scattering.

Figure 2: (a),(c) Pictures and (b) sketch of the fabricated miniaturized glass photonic system. (d) Working principle of the diopter-reflector system and (e) full system integrated with a CMOS chip.

CONCLUSIONS

We presented examples of micro-optical components and a miniaturized photonic system fabricated in glass with the FEMTOprint® laser-based 3D manufacturing technique. On the one hand, this technique can be further exploited to monolithically integrate not only optical micro-elements but also fluidic and mechanical micro-devices, which may have interesting implications, when precise alignment or co-packaging becomes critical. On the other hand, the FEMTOprint® manufacturing platform is already adapted for wafer-scale fabrication, from fast prototyping to pilot and volume production.

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CONTACT

* Rolando Ferrini; phone: +41 91 960 10 70; Email-address: rolando.ferrini@femtoprint.ch